

From the Rank Theorem to the Vaschy-Buckingham Theorem

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Abstract

This pedagogical note presents the mathematical foundations of the Vaschy-Buckingham theorem, known in fluid mechanics as the Π -theorem. The goal is to make explicit the link between this central result of dimensional analysis and the rank theorem of a linear map, as taught in first- or second-year undergraduate linear algebra. We show that the dimensionless condition can be reformulated as the search for the kernel of a linear map — the *dimensional matrix* — and that the number of independent dimensionless quantities is precisely the dimension of this kernel. The running example is the Stokes problem: the viscous drag exerted by a Newtonian fluid on a moving sphere, for which the method recovers the canonical form $F = \varphi(Re) \rho v^2 R^2$, bringing out the Reynolds number.

Keywords. Dimensional analysis, Vaschy-Buckingham theorem, rank theorem, kernel of a linear map, Reynolds number, Stokes problem.

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1 Introduction

In physics, every law relating physical quantities must be *homogeneous*: it must be invariant under a change of unit system. This constraint, often presented as a simple rule of thumb, has in reality a deep algebraic consequence: it reduces the number of *effectively* independent parameters of a problem, sometimes dramatically.

The *Vaschy-Buckingham theorem* [1] — often called the *II-theorem* — quantifies this reduction precisely. Its statement, familiar to engineers and physicists, asserts that a law among n physical quantities involving k fundamental dimensions can always be rewritten in terms of $p = n - r$ dimensionless numbers, where r is the rank of the dimensional matrix associated with the problem.

The objective of this note is to show that this result is a direct consequence of the *rank theorem* in linear algebra: $\dim(\ker A) = n - \text{rg}(A)$. This link is rarely made explicit in physics courses, which present the II-theorem as a practical tool without exposing the underlying mathematical structure.

The running example will be the *Stokes problem*: the drag force exerted by a viscous Newtonian fluid on a sphere moving at low speed. This problem is simple enough to be treated in full, yet rich enough to bring out the Reynolds number, one of the most important dimensionless numbers in fluid mechanics.

Outline. Section 2 reformulates the Stokes problem in the matrix formalism of dimensional analysis. Section 3 recalls the necessary linear algebra tools — rank, Gaussian elimination, rank theorem — and applies them to the dimensional matrix of the problem. Section 4 states the Vaschy-Buckingham theorem as a corollary of the rank theorem, introduces the notion of repeating variables, and develops the systematic method by sub-matrix decomposition and inversion (Section 4.3). Section 5 applies this method to the Stokes problem and explicitly constructs the two dimensionless numbers, bringing out the Reynolds number. Section 6 presents the general procedure and a summary table.

2 Matrix Reformulation of the Stokes Problem

2.1 Inventory of the relevant physical quantities

Consider a sphere of radius R moving at velocity v in a Newtonian fluid with dynamic viscosity η and mass density ρ . We seek to express the force F exerted by the fluid on the sphere.

Mathematical reformulation

We assume there exists a function ψ such that:

$$F = \psi(R, \eta, \rho, v) \quad (1)$$

The problem is thus described by $n = 5$ physical quantities. Equivalently, one can write the existence of an implicit relation Ψ such that:

$$\Psi(F, R, \eta, \rho, v) = 0 \quad (2)$$

Dimensional analysis works with this implicit form: it seeks a dimensionless combination of the five quantities.

We therefore seek a combination $\Pi = F^{x_F} R^{x_R} \eta^{x_\eta} \rho^{x_\rho} v^{x_v}$ that is *dimensionless*. Finding such a combination amounts to finding an exponent vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_F, x_R, x_\eta, x_\rho, x_v)^T$ satisfying certain linear constraints — which is precisely a linear algebra problem.

2.2 Dimensions of the relevant quantities

The five quantities are expressed in terms of $k = 3$ fundamental SI dimensions — mass M , length L , time T :

$$[F] = M L T^{-2}, \quad [R] = L, \quad [\eta] = M L^{-1} T^{-1}, \quad [\rho] = M L^{-3}, \quad [v] = L T^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Space of dimensional exponents

In general, the dimension of a quantity G_j is written:

$$[G_j] = M^{\alpha_{1j}} L^{\alpha_{2j}} T^{\alpha_{3j}} \dots \quad (4)$$

and is represented by the column vector $(\alpha_{1j}, \alpha_{2j}, \alpha_{3j}, \dots)^T \in \mathbb{R}^k$. The space of dimensions is therefore a vector space over \mathbb{R} , and each physical quantity is represented by an exponent vector.

2.3 The dimensional matrix

By arranging the exponent vectors as columns, we build the *dimensional matrix* $A \in \mathcal{M}_{k,n}(\mathbb{R})$:

$$A = \begin{matrix} & F & R & \eta & \rho & v \\ \begin{matrix} M \\ L \\ T \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -3 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix} \quad (5)$$

Column j of A is the exponent vector of the j -th quantity.

General case

For n quantities G_1, \dots, G_n involving k base dimensions d_1, \dots, d_k , the dimensional matrix A of size $k \times n$ is defined by:

$$A_{ij} = \alpha_{ij}, \quad \text{where} \quad [G_j] = d_1^{\alpha_{1j}} d_2^{\alpha_{2j}} \dots d_i^{\alpha_{ij}} \dots d_k^{\alpha_{kj}} \quad (6)$$

2.4 The dimensionless condition as a linear system

A monomial $\Pi = F^{x_F} R^{x_R} \eta^{x_\eta} \rho^{x_\rho} v^{x_v}$ is dimensionless if and only if the exponent of each base dimension is zero in $[\Pi]$. Using (3):

$$[\Pi] = \mathbf{M}^{x_F+x_\eta+x_\rho} \mathbf{L}^{x_F+x_R-x_\eta-3x_\rho+x_v} \mathbf{T}^{-2x_F-x_\eta-x_v} = \mathbf{M}^0 \mathbf{L}^0 \mathbf{T}^0 \quad (7)$$

which gives the linear system:

$$\begin{cases} x_F + x_\eta + x_\rho = 0 \\ x_F + x_R - x_\eta - 3x_\rho + x_v = 0 \\ -2x_F - x_\eta - x_v = 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

This system is rewritten in matrix form as:

$$A \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0} \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{x} = (x_F, x_R, x_\eta, x_\rho, x_v)^T \in \mathbb{R}^5$.

The key result is the following: **the exponent vectors of dimensionless monomials are exactly the elements of the kernel of A** . Finding dimensionless numbers is therefore a problem of computing the kernel of a linear map.

3 Linear Algebra Tools

3.1 Rank of a matrix

Definition of the rank

Let A be a $k \times n$ real matrix. The **rank** of A , denoted $\text{rg}(A)$, is the dimension of the image of the associated linear map:

$$\text{rg}(A) = \dim(\text{Im } A) \quad (10)$$

Equivalently, $\text{rg}(A)$ is the maximum number of linearly independent columns (or rows) of A . We always have $\text{rg}(A) \leq \min(k, n)$.

3.2 Computing the rank by Gaussian elimination

We apply *elementary row operations* that preserve the rank: swapping two rows, multiplying a row by a non-zero scalar, adding a multiple of one row to another. This reduces A to row echelon form: the rank is the number of non-zero rows obtained.

Applying this method to the dimensional matrix (5):

Initial matrix:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & -1 & -3 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Step 1. $R_2 \leftarrow R_2 - R_1$ and $R_3 \leftarrow R_3 + 2R_1$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -2 & -4 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The matrix is in echelon form with three non-zero rows. Therefore:

$$\text{rg}(A) = 3 \quad (13)$$

3.3 The rank theorem

Rank theorem

Let $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^k$ be a linear map with matrix $A \in \mathcal{M}_{k,n}(\mathbb{R})$. Then:

$$\dim(\ker f) + \dim(\operatorname{Im} f) = n \quad (14)$$

Since $\dim(\operatorname{Im} f) = \operatorname{rg}(A)$, we obtain:

$$\dim(\ker A) = n - \operatorname{rg}(A) \quad (15)$$

Interpretation. The vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)^T$ represents the exponents of a monomial $\Pi = G_1^{x_1} \cdots G_n^{x_n}$. The system $A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}$ imposes $\operatorname{rg}(A)$ independent linear constraints on these n exponents. By the rank theorem:

- $\operatorname{rg}(A)$ exponents are *bound*: their value is determined once the others are fixed;
- $n - \operatorname{rg}(A)$ exponents are *free*: they constitute the degrees of freedom of the solution space $\ker A$, each corresponding to an independent dimensionless monomial.

Applied to the Stokes problem:

$$\dim(\ker A) = n - \operatorname{rg}(A) = 5 - 3 = 2 \quad (16)$$

There are therefore exactly **two** independent dimensionless monomials.

4 From the Rank Theorem to the Vaschy-Buckingham Theorem

4.1 General statement

Vaschy-Buckingham theorem (Π -theorem)

Let a physical relation hold among n quantities G_1, \dots, G_n involving k fundamental dimensions. Let $r = \operatorname{rg}(A)$ be the rank of the dimensional matrix $A \in \mathcal{M}_{k,n}(\mathbb{R})$. Then there exist exactly:

$$p = n - r \quad (17)$$

independent dimensionless monomials $\Pi_1, \Pi_2, \dots, \Pi_p$, such that every homogeneous physical relation $f(G_1, \dots, G_n) = 0$ can be rewritten:

$$\Psi(\Pi_1, \Pi_2, \dots, \Pi_p) = 0 \quad (18)$$

The connection with linear algebra is summarised in the following table:

Correspondence: linear algebra \longleftrightarrow dimensional analysis

Linear algebra	\longleftrightarrow	Dimensional analysis
Linear map $A : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^k$	\longleftrightarrow	Dimensional matrix A
Unknowns $x_j \in \mathbb{R}$	\longleftrightarrow	Exponents of quantities G_j
System $A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}$	\longleftrightarrow	Dimensionless condition
$\dim(\text{Im } A) = r$	\longleftrightarrow	Number of dimensional constraints
$\dim(\ker A) = n - r$	\longleftrightarrow	Number of independent Π_i
Basis of $\ker A$	\longleftrightarrow	Family (Π_1, \dots, Π_p)
Free exponents	\longleftrightarrow	Non-repeating quantities
Bound exponents	\longleftrightarrow	Repeating quantities

4.2 Choice of repeating variables

In practice, a basis of $\ker A$ is constructed as follows. One chooses r so-called *repeating variables*, whose columns in A are linearly independent: they constitute the pivots of the system $A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}$, i.e. the quantities associated with *bound* exponents. The remaining $p = n - r$ quantities provide the *free* exponents: by setting each free exponent successively to 1 and the others to 0, one constructs p vectors forming a basis of $\ker A$, i.e. a family of p independent dimensionless monomials.

Remark. The choice of repeating variables is not unique. Different choices yield different bases of $\ker A$, hence different families (Π_i) — but all equivalent since they span the same vector space. The physicist chooses the repeating variables so as to bring out physically interpretable dimensionless numbers.

4.3 Systematic construction by sub-matrix decomposition

The repeating-variable method can be formulated in entirely algebraic terms, revealing its structure and underpinning a systematic computational procedure.

Partition of the dimensional matrix. Once the r repeating variables are chosen, the columns of A are reordered so that the repeating ones occupy the first r positions. One then partitions:

$$A = (A_b \mid A_d), \quad \mathbf{x} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{x}_b \\ \mathbf{x}_d \end{pmatrix}, \quad (19)$$

where $A_b \in \mathcal{M}_{k,r}(\mathbb{R})$ is the **base sub-matrix** (columns of the repeating variables) and $A_d \in \mathcal{M}_{k,p}(\mathbb{R})$ is the **dependent sub-matrix** (columns of the non-repeating quantities, $p = n - r$). The sub-vectors $\mathbf{x}_b \in \mathbb{R}^r$ and $\mathbf{x}_d \in \mathbb{R}^p$ contain the bound and free exponents, respectively.

By construction, the columns of A_b are linearly independent; that is, A_b is an **invertible** $r \times r$ square matrix ($\det A_b \neq 0$).

Solution by inversion. The system $A\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}$, rewritten using partition (19), gives:

$$A_b \mathbf{x}_b + A_d \mathbf{x}_d = \mathbf{0}. \quad (20)$$

Since A_b is invertible, we multiply (20) on the left by A_b^{-1} :

Fundamental formula of the repeating-variable method

$$\mathbf{x}_b = -A_b^{-1} A_d \mathbf{x}_d. \quad (21)$$

The exponents of the repeating variables are entirely determined by the free exponents: it suffices to compute the product $-A_b^{-1} A_d$.

Constructing a basis of $\ker A$. The vector $\mathbf{x}_d \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is free: any choice of \mathbf{x}_d defines, via (21), an element of $\ker A$. A canonical basis of the kernel is obtained by setting successively $\mathbf{x}_d = \mathbf{e}_j$ (the j -th canonical basis vector of \mathbb{R}^p), for $j = 1, \dots, p$. The corresponding j -th dimensionless number is:

$$\Pi_j = \prod_{i=1}^r G_i^{(x_b^{(j)})_i} \cdot G_{r+j}, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{x}_b^{(j)} = -A_b^{-1} \mathbf{a}_j^{(d)}, \quad (22)$$

$\mathbf{a}_j^{(d)}$ denoting the j -th column of A_d .

Global matrix form

By stacking the p solution vectors, one obtains the exponent matrix $X \in \mathcal{M}_{n,p}(\mathbb{R})$, whose columns are the exponent vectors of the Π_j :

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{x}_b^{(1)} & \cdots & \mathbf{x}_b^{(p)} \\ 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -A_b^{-1} A_d \\ I_p \end{pmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

Verification:

$$A X = (A_b \mid A_d) \begin{pmatrix} -A_b^{-1} A_d \\ I_p \end{pmatrix} = -A_b A_b^{-1} A_d + A_d = \mathbf{0}. \quad (24)$$

The columns of X indeed form a basis of $\ker A$.

Remark. Formula (21) is the matrix translation of what the physicist does intuitively: to make G_{r+j} dimensionless, one seeks which combination of powers of the repeating variables G_1, \dots, G_r exactly compensates its dimension. The inversion of A_b is the computation that performs this compensation systematically, without solving the system row by row.

5 Application to the Stokes Problem

5.1 Choice of repeating variables and physical motivation

From (16) we know that there are $p = 2$ dimensionless monomials. The Reynolds number $Re = \rho v R / \eta$ is the central dimensionless parameter of viscous fluid mechanics: it compares inertial effects to viscous ones. To make it appear directly, we choose as repeating variables the three quantities that compose it: ρ , v , and R .

Verification of linear independence

The columns of ρ , v , R in matrix (5) are:

$$\rho = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -3 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad v = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad R = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

Their determinant is:

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -3 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{vmatrix} = 1 \cdot \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{vmatrix} = 0 + 1 = 1 \neq 0 \quad (26)$$

The three columns are linearly independent: this choice is valid.

5.2 Applying the matrix method

The repeating variables $\{\rho, v, R\}$ give the partition (19) with columns reordered as (ρ, v, R, F, η) :

$$A_b = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -3 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad A_d = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \\ -2 & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (27)$$

We verified in the previous section that $\det A_b = 1 \neq 0$.

Computing A_b^{-1} . By Gaussian elimination on the augmented matrix $(A_b | I_3)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\begin{array}{ccc|ccc} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -3 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{array} \right) &\xrightarrow{R_2 \leftarrow R_2 + 3R_1} \left(\begin{array}{ccc|ccc} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 3 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{array} \right) &\xrightarrow{R_3 \leftarrow R_3 + R_2} \left(\begin{array}{ccc|ccc} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 3 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 3 & 1 & 1 \end{array} \right) \\ &\xrightarrow{R_2 \leftarrow R_2 - R_3} \left(\begin{array}{ccc|ccc} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 3 & 1 & 1 \end{array} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

We read off:

$$A_b^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 3 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (29)$$

Applying the fundamental formula (21).

$$-A_b^{-1}A_d = - \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 3 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \\ -2 & -1 \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 2 & 1 \\ 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -1 \\ -2 & -1 \\ -2 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The complete exponent matrix (23) is therefore:

$$X = \begin{matrix} & \Pi_1 & \Pi_2 \\ \begin{matrix} x_\rho \\ x_v \\ x_R \\ x_F \\ x_\eta \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} -1 & -1 \\ -2 & -1 \\ -2 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}. \quad (30)$$

We set each free exponent to 1 in turn.

5.3 Construction of the dimensionless monomials

Construction of Π_1 : the drag coefficient

The first column of X (30) gives, for $(x_F, x_\eta) = (1, 0)$:

$$x_\rho = -1, \quad x_v = -2, \quad x_R = -2$$

The exponent vector is $(x_F, x_R, x_\eta, x_\rho, x_v) = (1, -2, 0, -1, -2)$, giving:

$$\Pi_1 = \frac{F}{\rho v^2 R^2} \quad (31)$$

Dimensional check: $[\Pi_1] = \frac{\text{MLT}^{-2}}{\text{ML}^{-3}\cdot\text{L}^2\text{T}^{-2}\cdot\text{L}^2} = \frac{\text{MLT}^{-2}}{\text{MLT}^{-2}} = 1$

Π_1 is the *drag coefficient* (up to the numerical factor $\pi/8$ in the standard definition).

Construction of Π_2 : the Reynolds number

The second column of X (30) gives, for $(x_F, x_\eta) = (0, 1)$:

$$x_\rho = -1, \quad x_v = -1, \quad x_R = -1$$

The exponent vector is $(x_F, x_R, x_\eta, x_\rho, x_v) = (0, -1, 1, -1, -1)$, giving:

$$\Pi_2 = \frac{\eta}{\rho v R} = \frac{1}{Re} \quad (32)$$

Dimensional check: $[\Pi_2] = \frac{\text{ML}^{-1}\text{T}^{-1}}{\text{ML}^{-3}\cdot\text{L}\text{T}^{-1}\cdot\text{L}} = \frac{\text{ML}^{-1}\text{T}^{-1}}{\text{ML}^{-1}\text{T}^{-1}} = 1$.

Π_2 is the inverse of the *Reynolds number* $Re = \frac{\rho v R}{\eta}$.

5.4 The drag law and the Stokes law

The Vaschy-Buckingham theorem guarantees that the physical relation $\Psi(F, R, \eta, \rho, v) = 0$ can be rewritten:

$$\Phi\left(\frac{F}{\rho v^2 R^2}, Re\right) = 0 \quad (33)$$

Assuming that the drag coefficient can be expressed explicitly as a function of the Reynolds number, one obtains the *canonical form of the drag law*:

$$\frac{F}{\rho v^2 R^2} = \varphi(Re) \quad (34)$$

This result is remarkable: it asserts that the dimensionless drag coefficient of a sphere depends only on the Reynolds number, regardless of the fluid or the size of the sphere. This universal function can be represented as drag curves (C_D vs. Re).

Stokes regime ($Re \ll 1$). The analytical solution of the Navier-Stokes equations in the creeping-flow regime [3] gives $F = 6\pi \eta R v$. Substituting into (34):

$$\varphi(Re) = \frac{6\pi \eta R v}{\rho v^2 R^2} = \frac{6\pi}{\rho v R / \eta} = \frac{6\pi}{Re} \quad (35)$$

Dimensional analysis fixes the *form* of the law, but the constant 6π can only be determined by modelling or experiment: this is the intrinsic limitation of the method.

6 Summary and General Procedure

Dimensional analysis procedure

1. **Identify** the n relevant physical quantities and the k fundamental dimensions involved.
2. **Build** the dimensional matrix $A \in \mathcal{M}_{k,n}(\mathbb{R})$ whose column j is the exponent vector of $[G_j]$.
3. **Compute** $r = \text{rg}(A)$ by Gaussian elimination; deduce $p = n - r$: the number of independent dimensionless monomials.
4. **Choose** r repeating variables whose columns in A are linearly independent (verified by determinant or row reduction).
5. **Partition** $A = (A_b \mid A_d)$ and compute A_b^{-1} (by Gaussian elimination or cofactors); form the product $-A_b^{-1}A_d$: its columns give directly the exponents of the repeating variables in each Π_j .
6. **Read off** the complete exponent matrix: $X = \begin{pmatrix} -A_b^{-1}A_d \\ I_p \end{pmatrix}$ whose j -th column is the exponent vector of Π_j .
7. **Write** the physical law in the form: $\Pi_1 = \varphi(\Pi_2, \dots, \Pi_p)$

The following table summarises the different situations depending on the relationship between r and k :

Situation	Number of Π_i	Interpretation
$r = k$ (generic case)	$p = n - k$	Maximum reduction
$r < k$ (dimensional dependencies)	$p = n - r > n - k$	Partial reduction
$r = n$ (rare case, $n \leq k$)	$p = 0$	Completely determined law

In summary. The Vaschy-Buckingham theorem is the physical translation of the rank theorem: the dimension of the kernel of the dimensional matrix counts the number of dimensionless degrees of freedom of the problem. The “free” quantities of the linear system correspond to the independent Π_i monomials that parameterise all homogeneous physical laws.

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